

The 5 Key Success Factors for Successful Managers

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Abstract: *Complexity of the company's problems requires a reliable manager for the company growth and succeed, the strategy or program or project set by the manager determine the company growth or not. In practice, many challenges faced by managers in strategies or programs or projects not running properly. A successful manager is a manager who implement a strategy or program or project successfully and achieves measurable targets of the strategy or program or project. The measurement system using KPI is currently popular, but the skills to be an effective manager are still lacking which results in the target set in the KPI not being achieved. It becomes very important to discuss the fact that the skills of managers really need to be mastered become the main factor in the HR development strategy in achieving the company's targets through the KPIs of the managers. Therefore, an analysis is needed to become an effective manager in solving the complexity of the problems faced, conceptual research is needed based on the papers.. This study aims to determine the success factors of managers. Sample of 25 papers, leadership, communication skills and engagement traits are the three biggest factors influence a manager's success.*

Keywords: key success, successful managers

1. Introduction

The fact that some managers choose to resign is a problem for companies, especially small and medium-sized companies that prefer a leaner organizational structure. But actually what factors caused the resignation of these managers?. A small research company chooses too complicated and formalized an organization structure for its young age and limited size. It flounders in rigidity and bureaucracy for several years and is finally acquired by a larger company. Key executives of a retail store chain hold on to an organization structure long after it has served its purpose, because their power is derived from this structure. The company eventually goes into bankruptcy. A large bank disciplines a “rebellious” manager who is blamed for current control problems, when the underlying cause is centralized procedures that are holding back expansion into new markets. Many younger managers subsequently leave the bank, competition moves in, and profits are still declining. [1]

The problems of these companies, like those of many others, are rooted more in past decisions than in present events or outside market dynamics. Historical forces do indeed shape the future growth of organizations Yet management, in its haste to grow, often overlooks such critical developmental questions as: Where has our organization been? Where is it now? And what do the answers to these questions mean for where we are going? Instead, its gaze is fixed outward toward the environment and the future—as if more precise market projections will provide a new organizational identity. Companies fail to see that many clues to their future success lie within their own organizations and their evolving states of development. Moreover, the inability of management to understand its organization development problems can result in a company becoming “frozen” in its

present stage of evolution or, ultimately, in failure, regardless of market opportunities. [1].

The Leadership Crisis: All of the foregoing individualistic and creative activities are essential for the company to get off the ground. But therein lies the problem. As the company grows, larger production runs require knowledge about the efficiencies of manufacturing. Increased numbers of employees cannot be managed exclusively through informal communication; new employees are not motivated by an intense dedication to the product or organization. Additional capital must be secured, and new accounting procedures are needed for financial control. Thus the founders find themselves burdened with unwanted management responsibilities. So they long for the “good old days,” still trying to act as they did in the past. And conflicts between the harried leaders grow more intense. At this point a crisis of leadership occurs, which is the onset of the first revolution. Who is to lead the company out of confusion and solve managerial problems confronting it? Quite obviously, a strong manager is needed who has the necessary knowledge and skill to introduce new business techniques. But this is easier said than done. The founders often hate to step aside even though they are probably temperamentally unsuited to be managers. So here is the first critical developmental choice—to locate and install a strong business manager who is acceptable to the founders and who can pull the organization together. [1]

The leadership crisis as stated above, how should a manager be, how to distinguish good and bad managers, what should managers develop to its company growth?. Bad managers might make bad acquisitions simply because they are bad managers. Alternatively, bad managers have more incentive to acquire to assure the survival of the firm or to find new businesses they might be good at. The prediction is that acquisitions by bad managers are particularly disastrous. In

contrast, a plausible version of Roll's hubris hypothesis predicts that the worst acquisitions are made by well performing firms, since their managers are most likely to be infected by hubris. [2].

Have managers in your organization clearly identified the specific actions and behaviors that are off-limits? Every business faces the possibility that some employees may step outside the bounds of normally accepted business practices. Therefore, for any given business strategy, managers must determine what behaviors or actions could damage the business's reputation and declare those actions categorically off-limits. [3].

Why good companies do bad things ?

First of all, very few companies have a culture of debate. The boss says so, and we do it. It is a hierarchical, authoritarian system. Furthermore, in a world of rapid change, the worst thing you can do is suppress new ideas. The second reason is that businesses only look at financial measures of performance. What is the current profitability, sales, and so on? Another very important factor is that we discourage our employees from being whole people, from being people who have values, concerns, and cares of their own. We ask them to leave those things at the office door and simply focus on their tasks. People who focus only on their tasks are not whole people. They do not create well, they do not function well, they do not serve well. If we want to really use our employees well, we have to use all of their talents, all of their values, all of their beliefs. We have narrow networks. We talk to only a few people in the company, and we talk only to people at the country club, to other people like ourselves, our neighbours, and so on. The world is full of diversity, and if we do not engage that, we are going to be ever-narrower in our connections. We are thoughtless in our commitments. We do not actually think through the consequences of what we do and examine fully the impact of our decisions. [4]

We think ethics is for somebody else. We will hire a philosopher, a consultant in ethics who will tell us what is right and wrong. I do not know anybody in any company who does not instinctively know what is really right and wrong. There are important issues of subtlety. But I find it difficult to imagine that, for example, anybody in the tobacco industry absolutely believes it is right to sell cigarettes. Tobacco companies may think it is a smoker's choice. But is it right? And finally, there is a lack of self-examination. People simply do not reflect on themselves. They are in denial. Almost every psychological disorder has as its root denial ± failing to see oneself clearly. And I think almost every ethical issue comes from that sense of denial. We are good guys. We cannot possibly do the wrong thing. [4]

If you are thoughtful, if you actually reflect on yourself, if you have a wider set of networks and you are actually paying attention to the feedback you are getting from the world, then I think it is extremely possible to be perceived as doing the right thing. This is very important, because, I think, corporations are the most important engines for change. Most of us are in business because we want to do

``stuff," and we would rather do the right stuff than the wrong stuff. It is very important that many companies are moving ethics and responsibility from the periphery to the center of strategy[4].

Scholars and practitioners have championed the view that harmony and coordination between a firm's manufacturing and marketing functions are crucial antecedents to business success. Such coordination can occur via multiple routes, including norms that encourage information sharing, incentives and penalties that promote distortion-free knowledge transfers between departments, and the pursuit of integrated goals. Fisher et al argue that the lack of such coordination has led to many business failures, In many firms, manufacturing operates as a cost center that seeks lower costs and efficient scale economies. Firms may employ incentive systems to communicate these objectives to manufacturing personnel. For example, at glass manufacturer Libbey-Owens-Ford, manufacturing managers are compensated based on cost minimization, and continuously seek efficiencies in the production process. In contrast, marketing typically operates as a profit or revenue center, with control over price and other marketing elements. We term this situation the "conflicting-objectives puzzle," because one would reasonably expect that centrally coordinated decisions made by the owners of the firm would yield higher profits. [5].

2. Manager, Success & Success Manager Definition

Manager is a job title that's used in organizations to designate an employee who leads functions or departments, and often employees. A manager is assigned to a particular level on an organizational chart. The manager's role and job description are at a pay grade or job classification level that integrates functions and departments for the implementation of success. [6]

The most obvious beginning and ending of the person of the manager is bound up with his skill in management. The manager at all levels is responsible for planning. Planning must look to levels of employment. Since men cannot gain the advantages of material security or private property in the face of uncertain employment, the manager must see that his planning obligates the firm to reasonably continuous employment once a person is placed on the payroll. [7]

The manager must be mature and possess character. Character is indicated by words such as integrity, fairness, ability to inspire, teach and develop. He must have a certain mental attitude and facility as his talents will allow. He should be motivated to serve people through their industrial economy without making industrial economy his god. He must understand the responsibilities and obligations which his environment demands.[7].

As moral manager, the CEO is thought of as the Chief Ethics Officer of the organization, creating a strong ethics message that gets employees' attention and influences their thoughts and behaviours. Both are necessary. To be perceived as an ethical leader, it is not enough to just be an ethical person. An executive ethical leader must also find

ways to focus the organization's attention on ethics and values and to infuse the organization with principles that will guide the actions of all employees. An executive's reputation for ethical leadership may be more important now than ever in this new organizational era where more employees are working independently, off site, and without direct supervision. [8]

Developing a reputation for ethical leadership depends upon how others perceive the leader on two dimensions: as a moral person and as a moral manager. Being a moral person encompasses who you are, what you do, and what you decide as well as making sure that others know about this dimension of you as a person. Being a moral manager involves being a role model for ethical Moral Person and Moral Manager: How Executives Develop a Reputation for Ethical conduct, communicating regularly about ethics and values, and using the reward system to hold everyone accountable to the values and standards. Ethical leadership pays dividends in employee pride, commitment, and loyalty—all particularly important in a full employment economy in which good companies strive to find and keep the best people. [8].

Success is something that you have to define for yourself, and no one can do it for you. Success could mean a sense of giving back to the world and making a difference. It could mean a sense of accomplishment and career progression. [9]

According to Dictionary.com, success means **“the accomplishment of one's goals, the attainment of wealth, position, honours, or the like”**.

25 quotes about success

1. *“We think success is a one-way street. So we do everything that leads up to success, but then we get there. We figure we've made it, we sit back in our comfort zone, and we actually stop doing everything that made us successful. And it doesn't take long to go downhill. Success isn't a one-way street...it's a continuous journey”*
– Richard St. John, entrepreneur and success analyst.
2. *“Define success on your own terms, achieve it by your own rules, and build a life you're proud to live.”*
– Anne Sweeney, an American businesswoman, co-chair of Disney Media, and President of Disney Channel from 1996-2014.
3. *“Success is not greedy, as people think, but insignificant. That is why it satisfies nobody.”*
–Lucius Annaeus Seneca, Roman philosopher, and dramatist.
4. *“Success is not final; failure is not fatal: It is the courage to continue that counts.”*–
– Most often attributed to Winston S. Churchill, British politician and Prime Minister of United Kingdom from 1940-1945 and 1951-1955.
5. *“Some failure in life is inevitable. It is impossible to live without failing at something, unless you live so cautiously that you might as well not have lived at all—in which case, you fail by default.”*
– JK Rowling, British writer, philanthropist, film, and television producer, best known for writing the Harry Potter series, in her 2008 Harvard Commencement Address.
6. *“The road to success and the road to failure are almost exactly the same.”*
– Colin R. Davis, British conductor.
7. *“We need to accept that we won't always make the right decisions, that we'll screw up royally sometimes – understanding that failure is not the opposite of success, it's part of success.”*
– Arianna Huffington, co-founder, and EIC of The Huffington Post.
8. *“Would you like me to give you a formula for success? It's quite simple, really: Double your rate of failure. You are thinking of failure as the enemy of success. But it isn't at all. You can be discouraged by failure or you can learn from it, so go ahead and make mistakes. Make all you can. Because remember that's where you will find success.”*
– Thomas J. Watson, American businessman, and industrialist.
9. *“If you are successful, it is because somewhere, sometime, someone gave you a life or an idea that started you in the right direction. Remember also that you are indebted to life until you help some less fortunate person, just as you were helped.”*
– Melinda Gates, philanthropist, and co-founder of the Bill & Melinda Gates Foundation.
10. *“Success is no accident. It is hard work, perseverance, learning, studying, sacrifice and most of all, love of what you are doing or learning to do.”*
– Pelé, famous Brazilian footballer (soccer) player.
11. *“Successful people do what unsuccessful people are not willing to do. Don't wish it were easier; wish you were better.”*
– Jim Rohn, American entrepreneur, writer, and motivational speaker.
12. *“What you do today matters. What you do every day matters. Successful people just do the things that seem to make no difference in the act of doing them and they do them over and over and over until the compound effect kicks in.”*
— Jeff Olson, author, founder and CEO of Nerium International, in *The Slight Edge: Secret to a Successful Life*
13. *“The difference between successful people and others is how long they spend time feeling sorry for themselves.”*
— Barbara Corcoran, founder of The Corcoran Group real estate empire and cast member of ABC's *Shark Tank*.
14. *“Keep on going, and the chances are that you will stumble on something, perhaps when you are least expecting it. I never heard of anyone ever stumbling on something sitting down.”*
— Charles F. Kettering, inventor, engineer, businessman, and founder of Delco, the electronics subsidiary of GM.
15. *“Dreams are lovely. But they are just dreams. Fleeting, ephemeral. Pretty. But dreams do not come true just because you dream them. It's hard work that makes things happen. It's hard work that creates change.”*
— Shonda Rhimes, American television producer, screenwriter, and author, who is best known for creating *Grey's Anatomy*, in her book *Year of Yes: How to*

- Dance It Out, Stand in the Sun, and Be Your Own Person.
16. "Success isn't about how much money you make; it's about the difference you make in people's lives." — Michelle Obama, American lawyer, writer, and First Lady of the United States from 2009-2017, in a speech to the Democratic National Convention in 2012.
 17. "The price of success is hard work, dedication to the job at hand, and the determination that whether we win or lose, we have applied the best of ourselves to the task at hand." — Vince Lombardi, American football coach, and executive.
 18. "Do the one thing you think you cannot do. Fail at it. Try again. Do better the second time. The only people who never tumble are those who never mount the high wire." — Oprah Winfrey, American television mogul, talk show host, actress, producer, and philanthropist.
 19. "Money won't create success, the freedom to make it will." — Nelson Mandela, South African anti-apartheid revolutionary and President of South Africa from 1994 to 1999.
 20. "Failure is the key to success; each mistake teaches us something." — Morihei Ueshiba, athlete, martial artist, and founder of aikido.
 21. "Success is a lousy teacher; it seduces smart people into thinking they can't lose." — Bill Gates, an American businessman, investor, author, philanthropist, and founder of Microsoft Corporation.
 22. "Winners are not afraid of losing. But losers are. Failure is part of the process of success. People who avoid failure also avoid success." — Robert T. Kiyosaki, American businessman and author, in his book Rich Dad, Poor Dad.
 23. "I always did something I was a little not ready to do. I think that's how you grow. When there's that moment of 'Wow, I'm not really sure I can do this,' and you push through those moments, that's when you have a breakthrough."

- Marissa Mayer, former CEO of Yahoo.
24. "Success is assured when a person fears the pain of regret more than the pain of the process." — Orrin Woodward, best selling author, founder, and Chairman of the Board of Life and Obstacles Press.
 25. "Success seems to be connected to action. Successful people keep moving. They make mistakes, but they don't quit." — Conrad Hilton, businessman, and founder of Hilton Hotels chain. [10].

According to the definition of success and the manager described above, a **successful manager** is a person who **manages and achieves the targets or goals** of the unit or department.

The profile of a success Manager in a Public Hospital is **framed by knowledge and skills that respond to the duties and competences** of a contemporary Manager in Healthcare Management. In order to cope with the administrative challenges of a public hospital under its present legal form, it is necessary to design a business plan, taking advantage of the potentials he comes across studying its environment. [11]

3. The Challenges, Managers Faced

Complexity of the company's problems requires a reliable manager for the company growth and succeed, the strategy or program or project set by the manager determine the company growth or not. In practice, many challenges faced by managers in strategies or programs or projects not running properly.

Certainly, Successful managers face challenges well, implement strategies and achieve the goals or targets of the units.

Managers in their work are sure facing these challenges, these challenges as in the table below :

Table I: Manager Challenges

No	Challenges findings (all about)	Source/Ref
1	Personal issues/attitude/motivation	[12][13][14][16][21]
2	Scheduling/work load	[12][19]
3	Staff Management/hiring/placement/man power	[12][13][18]
4	Resource Management/inventory	[12][13]
5	Organisational demands/organisational Support	[12][13][20]
6	Change Management	[12][22]
7	Conflict Management	[12][13]
8	Multi disciplinary coordination/communication/tourist	[12][13][17][20][21][22]
9	Range of support from the organisation	[12]
10	Managing the high expectations of others	[12]
11	Poor inter-unit Communication	[12][20][21]
12	Information system/Management System	[12][14][20]
13	Work-family issue	[13]
14	Marketing relationship/Cust complaint/Consumer Relation	[13][17][20]
15	Managing Budget/budget cuts/pricing/Investment	[13][14][12][20]
16	Boss/owner need; co-worker relationship	[13][18]
17	Dealing with government/legal aspect/regulatory	[13][14][17][18][20]
18	Vison/Mission/Strategy/program/brand management unclear	[13][14][15][17][18][19][20]
19	Physical environment/environment issue	[13][14][18][21]

20	Productivity	[14]
21	Business Competitor	[15]
22	Technology	[15][17][18][20]
23	Gap Responsibility/skill/competency	[16][17][20][21]
24	Education	[17]
25	Machine/maintenance	[18]
26	Operation/process	[18]
27	Health/insurance/benefits	[20]

The table above illustrates the challenges faced by managers in achieving their targets. The three biggest challenges are understanding the vision, mission and strategies that have been determined, then ineffective coordination and communication and personal issues or attitudes.

The following graph illustrates the challenges faced by managers

Figure 1: Manager challenges stratification

4. The Key Success Factors (KSF)

A Successful Manager

Through the mapping of 25 papers, the author finds the success factors the manager achieves the targets or goals of the unit they leads.

Ability to lead, the ability to communicate effectively and engagement traits or emotional intelligence, it's determines the success of managers in facing challenges in achieving departmental targets or goals.

The Quotes of 25 papers; [23] – [47]

Some of the success factors for virtual teams are no different from success factors for face-to-face teams, and certainly three of the major domains - communication, culture, and project management [23]. For practitioners, certification has been shown to be only one important asset for the project manager. Our results infer that obtaining certification does not guarantee good project managers. Two other constructs seem to be equally important: (1) engagement traits and (2) experience [24]. In a complex project setting, project managers who are confronted with a difficult situation would be able to regulate their emotions to work towards a productive outcome [25].

We want to emphasize that the deliberate design of iterative communication mechanisms is a vital component of the adaptive management process and can contribute to wide-ranging positive outcomes in social-ecological systems. We propose that managers can embed a more deliberate perspective on public communication in the practice of adaptive co-management by working through a process that

includes the following: setting social-ecological outcomes; co-prioritizing projects with stakeholders; codesigning both restoration projects and iterative engagement mechanisms; co-implementing; co-monitoring; co-evaluating ecological, stakeholder, and learning successes; communicating about successes and failures internally and externally; adjusting methods and priorities; assessing problems; and resetting social-ecological outcome [26].

The first goal of this study was to investigate the most important competencies among the traditional set presented in the literature. According to project managers, communication, commitment and leadership are the most important. Not surprisingly, “communication” ranks first. According to the PMI, communication is key in project management. In the context of project management, “communication involves several dimensions, such as written and oral, formal and informal, vertical and horizontal, and internal (within the project) and external (customers, etc.) [27]

In analyzing the individual variables within these categories, Nursing Managers identified the following five variables as being most important to the success of their role (on a 5-point scale): • communication (4.96);• negotiation (4.71);• critical thinking (4.70);• balance between work and home (4.70);• conflict management (4.69). [28]

Lee-Kelley et al. set out to find which Project Management Knowledge Areas are critical to project success and whether the project manager’s leadership style influences his or her perception of control. What they did find was the project manager’s leadership style influenced his or her perception of success on the project. They suggest: [There is] a significant relationship between the leader’s perception of project success and his or her personality and contingent experiences. Thus the inner confidence and self-belief from personal knowledge and experience are likely to play an important role in a manager’s ability to deliver a project successfully. [29]. Leadership will have a positive relationship with project and project management process success [30].

Managers in India have a clear opportunity to retain more of their people by showing strong personal commitment and interest in each employee. Hold career discussions. Meeting to discuss career progress and plans on a regular basis helped to demonstrate manager support because it opened the dialogue on employee interests and motivators [31].

For managers in nontechnical jobs (61 % of the managers in the sample), a positive association has shown at 8 and 16 years after testing between the predicted leadership motive pattern and subsequent promotion in the company. This

means that senior managers in jobs that do not focus on the engineering aspects of the business who (a) are concerned about influencing others, (b) are less concerned about being liked, and (c) have a moderate to high degree of self-control are more likely to succeed than other senior managers in jobs that do not focus on engineering [32].

The “hard” technical skills are not enough to ensure positive results in project management. This does not imply that IT project managers should abandon the technical competencies that they developed throughout their careers. However, it does imply that IT project managers should combine technical skills with interpersonal and managerial competencies so they are better equipped to achieve project success. This research also shows that communication skills are necessary not only in the relationship between the project manager and his/her team, but that an effective project manager should be able to communicate at multiple levels [33].

The ultimate aim of the project manager is to establish trust in managing outcomes—and project leadership plays a critical role in establishing trust. Technology tools assist knowledge sharing, team development, efficiency, and effectiveness, motivating factors that can lead to knowledge sharing, team development, and innovation are dependent on the project leadership role in establishing trust and open communications [34].

The personnel’s possessing the strong personality traits regarding Extraversion and Openness to experience, prove to be most appropriate candidates as project managers [35].

Transformational leadership and soft skills on project managers will help foster more collaborative working relationships, encourage a team approach to problem solving and a willingness to find cost-effective and innovative solutions for the benefit of individuals, teams, clients and the industry as a whole [36].

Manager’s work quality and management efficiency are important factors for organization productivity. The quality and efficiency depend on manager’s competence, professionalism and experience. The important personal traits are considered responsibility, creativity, integrity and honesty [37].

An important difference between a model for the selection of a chief executive and one for the selection of key operational managers is the diversity of possible strategies at the various business levels, and thus many potentially different types of managers [38].

Considers the many demands facing managers in modern organizations, particularly following the effects of downsizing and flattened organizational structures. Managers have to be concerned with, variously, product and/or service quality, financial planning and accountability, organizational change, risk and project management, efficient use of resources (especially human resources), teamwork and leadership, stress and counselling [39].

The American Organization of Nurse Executives (AONE), as described by Turley,1 established three key areas for the organization's 2003-2005 Strategic Plan: stewards of leadership, patient care delivery systems, and the work environment [40].

Personality traits of the project manager have a special role and contribution to the success of the project. This study aims at describing the extent of variation in the performance of the project explained by the personality traits of the project manager which include his authority, extroversion, introversion, and vision [41].

The report revealed that the distinctive features of the managers include: • a very strong personal motivation to assist the Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander community; • a willingness to take on a leadership role and initiate change within the community; • a direct sense of responsibility and accountability to the community; and • a desire to work outside the bureaucratic processes that often create barriers to success [42]

The main features of hotel manager succeed are professionalism, leadership and communicative abilities, the ability to motivate people, to organize his/her time and to cope with stress, and personal qualities and skills [43]

Program management is a tough job. Meeting cost, schedule, and performance requirements on challenging acquisition programs takes both skill and teamwork by the project team or program office. But at the heart of effective performance is the program manager (PM). Future PMs appear to be doing well in many of the top rated importance categories, such as communication, integrity, and people skills. We may think of program management as an effective combination of technical and management skills. But the view from the trenches is that the successful PM is first and foremost a leader. And leadership is all about people [44].

Most of the skills needed beyond five years shift towards leadership and management skills, which are not obtained through formal education [45].

The project manager’s leadership style influences the project team and can contribute to project success. They found that a project manager’s emotional competence, EQ, had a meaningful contribution to project success, in most project situations. Managerial competence, MQ, of the project manager was sometimes meaningful, and intellectual competence, IQ, was usually not correlated to success [46].

Trust was found to be significantly related to sales, profits and employee turnover in the restaurant industry [47].

Table II: The Key Success Factors (KSF)

A Successful Manager

No	The Rank of Key Success Factors (KSF) A Successful Manager	Source/Ref
1	Leadership	[27][29][30][32][36][39][40][42][43][44][45][46]
2	Communication	[23][26][27][28][31][33][34][43][44]
3	Engagement traits	[24][26][35][37][41]
4	Skills (Hard, Soft,	[36][43][44][45]

	Managerial)	
5	Project Management	[23][26][29]
6	Experience	[24][37]
7	Commitment	[27][31]
8	Trust	[34][47]
9	Professionalism	[37][43]
10	Stress	[39][43]
11	Motivation	[42][43]
12	Culture	[23]
13	Emotional intelligence	[25]
14	Negotiation	[28]
15	Critical thinking	[28]
16	Balance between work & home	[28]
17	Conflict Management	[28]
18	Competence	[37]
19	Strategy Concept	[38]
20	Product/service quality	[39]
21	Financial planning	[39]
22	Organizational change	[39]
23	Efficient of resource	[39]
24	Teamwork	[39]
25	Counseling	[39]
26	Responsibility	[42]
27	Desire	[42]
28	Personal Quality	[42]
29	Integrity	[44]

As the table shown, the five biggest success factors for managers are (1) leadership skills, (2) communication skills, (3) engagement traits, (4) skills and (5) project / program management.

Figure 2: KSF Success Manager

5. Conclusion

The manager at all levels is responsible for planning. Planning must look to levels of employment. Since men cannot gain the advantages of material security or private property in the face of uncertain employment, the manager must see that his planning obligates the firm to reasonably continuous employment once a person is placed on the payroll. The manager must be mature and possess character. Character is indicated by words such as integrity, fairness, ability to inspire, teach and develop. He must have a certain mental attitude and facility as his talents will allow.

In practice, as a manager usually faced with various challenges, unclear vision, mission and strategy, ineffective coordination and communication, and personal issues or attitudes, through strong and resilient leadership, improving communication skills and engagement traits, increasing skills and focus on the program or strategy implementation, target managers achieved and getting the predicate “Successful Manager”.

The five biggest success factors for managers are (1) leadership skills, (2) communication skills, (3) engagement traits, (4) skills and (5) project / program management to get the predicate “Successful Manager”.

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